

Supplementary Material

Design, Synthesis, and Biological Evaluation of Tetrazol-2-yl-acetamides as Novel Antitubercular Agents

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- Experimental methods and materials, and representative synthesis procedures
- Biological assay protocols
- ¹H spectra for compounds

Experimental Methods and Materials

All chemicals were commercially available except those whose synthesis is described or referenced.

Representative Synthetic Procedures and Spectral Data

General Synthesis as exemplified for sALT629 (P1)

2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P1**) and 2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1H-tetrazol-1-yl)acetamide (**P1B**)

Step a: To a stirred solution of 4-hydroxybenzonitrile **1** (7 g, 0.0588 mol) in dry DMF (70 mL), were added KI (9.7 g, 0.0588 mol), K₂CO₃ (16 g, 0.115 mol) and 1-bromo-2-methylpropane **2** (12 g, 0.0875 mol) at rt and stirred reaction mixture at 120 °C for 12 h. After completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was quenched with water (150 mL) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 x 50 mL). Combined organic layers washed with brine solution (100 mL). The organic layer was separated out and dried over Na₂SO₄. Concentrated under vacuum to obtain crude product, which was purified by column chromatography in 30% ethyl acetate in hexanes to get pure 4-isobutoxybenzonitrile **3** (4g, 38.85%). LCMS: 176.1 (M+H)⁺

Step b: To a stirred solution of **3** (3 g, 0.0171 mol) in dry toluene (30 mL) were added NaN₃ (2.7 g, 0.0415 mol) and TEA.HCl (5.7 g, 0.0415 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred at 120 °C for 24 h. After completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was quenched with ice cold water (100 mL) and product was extracted with dichloromethane (3 x 30 mL). Combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under vacuum to get 5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazole **4** (4g, 100%) which was used for next step without further purification. LCMS: 219.2 (M+H)⁺

Step c: To a stirred solution of **4** (3 g, 0.0137 mol) in DMF (30 mL) were added Cs₂CO₃ (13.2 g, 0.0406 mol) and 2-bromoacetamide **5** (2 g, 0.0145 mol) at rt and stirred at 120 °C for 2 h. After completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was quenched with ice cold water (100 mL). and product was extracted with dichloromethane (3 x 30 mL). Combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄ and dried under vacuum. The crude product was purified by column chromatography

in 50% ethyl acetate in hexanes to get pure 4-isobutoxybenzonitrile 2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P1**) (1.3 g, 34.35%) and 2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1H-tetrazol-1-yl)acetamide (**P1B**) (0.2 g, 5.28%) as white solid. **P1**: LCMS: 304.9 (M+H)⁺; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.99-7.97 (m, 2H), 7.87 (s, 1H), 7.54 (s, 1H), 7.11 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 5.44 (s, 2H), 3.83 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.08-2.02 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 6H). **P1B**: LCMS: 304.9 (M+H)⁺; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.90 (s, 1H), 7.68 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.53 (s, 1H), 7.13 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 5.17 (s, 2H), 3.83 (m, 2H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 6H).

3-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)propanamide (**P2**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 290.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.96 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.52 (s, H), 7.10 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.01 (s, H), 4.86 (m, 2H), 3.82 (d, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 2.67 (m, 2H), 2.05 (m, 1H), 1.0 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)propanamide (**P3**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 290.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.97 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.84 (s, H), 7.51 (s, 1H), 7.10 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 5.61 (m, H), 3.18 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 2.85 (m, d, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H), 0.99 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)-2-methylpropanamide (**P4**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 304.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.97 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.49 (m, 2H), 7.08 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), , 3.81 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 1.94 (s, 6H), 0.99 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetic acid (**P5**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 277.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.98 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.11 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 5.73 (s, 2H), 3.82 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 3.33 (br s, 1H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 1.94 (s, 6H), 0.99 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 6H).

Methyl 2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetate (**P6**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 291.1; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.99 (d, $J = 12$ Hz, 2H), 7.13 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 5.89 (s, 2H), 3.84 (d, $J = 4.0$ Hz, 2H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 1.02 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)-N-methylacetamide (**P7**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 290.1; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 8.37 (s, 1H), 7.99 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.10 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 5.44 (s, 2H), 3.82 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H), 2.66 (m, 3H), 2.05 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 6H).

2-((5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)methyl)oxazole (**P8**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 300.1; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 8.20 (s, 1H), 7.96 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.29 (s, 1H), 7.09 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.26 (s, 2H), 3.81 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.05 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 6H).

2-(2-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-5-yl)acetamide (**P9**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 276.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 7.97 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.67 (br s, 1H), 7.19 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 3.86 – 3.85 (m, 4H), 2.06 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(4-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-1,2,3-triazol-2-yl)acetamide (P10)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 275.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 8.17 (s, 1H), 7.75 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.65 (s, 1H), 7.37 (s, 1H), 7.02 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 5.09 (s, 2H), 3.80 (m, 2H), 2.06 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 6H).

2-(4-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)acetamide (P11)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 275.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 8.39 (s, 1H), 7.77 (d, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.43 (s, 1H), 7.01 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 5.09 (s, 2H), 3.79 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 6H).

2-(3-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1H-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)acetamide (P12)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 275.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 8.45 (s, 1H), 7.77 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.67 (s, 1H), 7.35 (s, 1H), 7.01 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 4.87 (s, 2H), 3.78 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(4-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetamide (P13)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 274.3; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 8.01 (s, 1H), 7.79 (s, 1H), 7.46 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.27 (s, 1H), 6.88 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 4.74 (s, 2H), 3.73 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H), 2.02 (m, 1H), 0.98 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 6H).

2-(3-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetamide (P14)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 274.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.70 (m, 3H), 7.50 (s, 1H), 7.28 (s, 1H), 6.95 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.62 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.77 (s, 2H), 3.77 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H), 2.03 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(4-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1H-imidazol-1-yl)acetamide (**P15**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 274.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.64- 7.57 (m, 3H), 7.41 (s, 1H), 7.28 (s, 1H), 6.90 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.63 (s, 2H), 3.73 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.02 (m, 1H), 0.98 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 6H).

2-(3-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)acetamide (**P16**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 276.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.91 (m, 2H), 7.32 (m, 2H), 7.09 (m, 2H), 3.95- 3.82 (m, 4H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 1.09 (m, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P17**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 276.3; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.89 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.76 (s, 1H), 7.29 (s, 1H), 7.13 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 3.87 (s, 2H), 3.83 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)acetamide (**P18**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 276.3; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 8.02 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.69 (s, 1H), 7.22 (s, 1H), 7.16 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 2H), 3.87 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 3.65 (s, 2H), 2.06 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 6H).

2-(2-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)oxazol-5-yl)acetamide (**P19**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 275.3; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.87 (m, 3H), 7.43 (s, 1H), 7.06 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.99 (s, 1H), 3.81 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 3.36 (s, 2H), 2.02 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(3-(4-isobutoxyphenyl)isoxazol-5-yl)acetamide (**P20**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 275.2; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.76 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.64 (s, 1H), 7.03 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 6.78 (s, 1H), 3.80 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 3.69 (s, 2H), 2.03 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(2-fluoro-4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P21**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 294.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.98 (m, 1H), 7.89 (s, 1H), 7.55 (s, 1H), 7.05 (m, 1H), 6.97 (m, 1H), 5.48 (s, 2H), 3.87 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.05 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(2-chloro-4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P22**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 310.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.86 (s, 1H), 7.84 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.55 (s, 1H), 7.22 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 7.10 (dd, *J* = 10, 2.8 Hz, 1H), 5.48 (s, 2H), 3.87 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.04 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(3-fluoro-4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P23**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 294.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.84-7.79 (m, 3H), 7.57 (s, 1H), 7.36 (m, 1H), 5.47 (s, 2H), 3.87 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.06 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(3-chloro-4-isobutoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (P24)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 294.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 8.03 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.98 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.90 (s, 1H), 7.57 (s, 1H), 7.33 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 5.47 (s, 2H), 3.93 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.09 (m, 1H), 1.02 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxy-2-methylphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (P25)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 290.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.85 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.54 (s, 1H), 6.94 (m, 2H), 5.45 (s, 2H), 3.80 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 2H), 2.53 (s, 3H), 2.03 (m, 1H), 0.99 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxy-3-methylphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P26**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 290.1; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.87-7.85 (m, 3H), 7.55 (s, 1H), 7.08 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 5.44 (s, 2H), 3.84 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.25 (s, 3H), 2.08 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxy-2-methoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P27**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 306.1; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.86 (s, 1H), 7.76 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.52 (s, 1H), 6.73 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.68 (dd, $J = 8.4, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 5.43 (s, 2H), 3.85-3.84 (m, 3H), 2.05 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-isobutoxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P28**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 306.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.89 (s, 1H), 7.63 – 7.53 (m, 3H), 7.12 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 5.45 (s, 2H), 3.86 (s, 3H), 3.81 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.05 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(5-isobutoxy)pyridin-2-yl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P29**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 277.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 8.44 (d, $J = 2.8$ Hz, 1H), 8.07 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.89 (s, 1H), 7.57 (m, 2H), 5.47 (s, 2H), 3.91 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.07 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-(isobutylamino)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P30**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 275.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.85 (s, 1H), 7.75 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.52 (s, 1H), 6.68 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 6.23 (m, 1H), 5.38 (s, 2H), 2.89 (m, 2H), 1.86 (m, 1H), 0.95 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 6H).

2-(5-(4-(cyclopropylmethoxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P31**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 274.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.96 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.87 (s, 1H), 7.54 (s, 1H), 7.09 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 5.44 (s, 2H), 3.89 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 2H), 1.24 (m, 1H), 0.58 (m, 2H), 0.35 (m, 2H).

2-(5-(4-(cyclobutylmethoxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P32**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 288.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.97 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.87 (s, 1H), 7.54 (s, 1H), 7.10 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 5.44 (s, 2H), 4.02 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H), 2.75 (m, 1H), 2.08 (m, 2H), 1.88 (m, 4H).

2-(5-(4-(cyclopentylmethoxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P33**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 302.1; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.98 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.88 (s, 1H), 7.55 (s, 1H), 7.11 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 5.45 (s, 2H), 3.92 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H), 2.31 (m, 1H), 1.78 (m, 2H), 1.57 (m, 4H), 1.34 (m, 2H).

2-(5-(4-(cyclohexylmethoxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P34**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 316.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.96 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.88 (s, 1H), 7.55 (s, 1H), 7.09 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 5.44 (s, 2H), 3.85 (d, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 1.82 (m, 1H), 1.67 (m, 4H), 1.24 (m, 4H), 1.03 (m, 2H).

2-(5-(4-((2,2-difluorocyclopentyl)methoxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P35**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 338.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.99 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.89 (s, 1H), 7.56 (s, 1H), 7.12 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 5.45 (s, 2H), 4.02 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.56 (m, 1H), 2.21-1.95 (m, 5H), 1.65 (m, 1H).

2-(5-(4-(oxetan-3-ylmethoxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P36**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 290.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.99 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 7.87 (s, 1H), 7.55 (s, 1H), 7.14 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 5.44 (s, 2H), 4.72 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 4.46 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 4.29 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 3.42 (m, 1H).

2-(5-(4-(benzyloxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P37**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 310.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.00 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.90 (s, 1H), 7.57 (s, 1H), 7.50-7.35 (m, 6H), 7.20 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 5.46 (s, 2H), 5.19 (s, 2H).

2-(5-(4-(pyridin-2-ylmethoxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P38**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 311.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.61 (d, *J* = 4.4 Hz, 2H), 8.01 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.86 (m, 1H), 7.56 (d, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 7.38 (m, 1H), 7.22 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 5.46 (s, 2H), 5.27 (s, 2H).

2-(5-(4-(2-cyclopropylpropoxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P39**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 302.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.99 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.88 (s, 1H), 7.54 (s, 1H), 7.12 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 5.45 (s, 2H), 4.06 (m, 1H), 3.93 (m, 1H), 1.24 (m, 1H), 1.08 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 3H), 0.70 (m, 1H), 0.43 (m, 2H), 0.24 (m, 1H), 0.14 (m, 1H).

2-(5-(4-(2-cyclobutylpropoxy)phenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl)acetamide (**P40**)

LCMS [ESI, M+1]: 316.1; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.00 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.89 (s, 1H), 7.55 (s, 1H), 7.13 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 5.46 (s, 2H), 3.80 (m, 2H), 0.91-0.89 (m, 7H), 0.30 (m, 4H)

Biological assay protocols

Bacterial Strains. *Mtb* H37Rv (ATCC 27294) and H37Ra were used as reference strains. The other strains of *Mtb* were clinical isolates from our laboratory collection. The mycobacterial strains included in the study were maintained in the Middlebrook 7H9 medium (Difco) supplemented 0.5% (vol/vol) glycerol, 0.05% (vol/vol) tyloxapol and 10% (vol/vol) Oleic acid Albumin Dextrose catalase Complex OADC to ensure uniform conditions across species and to prevent oleic acid-related metabolic variability. Mycobacterial strains were plated on Middlebrook 7H10 (Difco) agar plates. When appropriate, hygromycin B (Roche) was added to the media.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) Assay. MIC values were determined using ten twofold serial dilutions of test compounds in Middlebrook 7H9 broth supplemented with either (i) 10% OADC and glycerol or (ii) 0.01% (w/v) cholesterol, 0.5% (w/v) Casitone, and 50 mM 2-(N-morpholino)ethanesulfonic acid (MES), pH adjusted to 6.7. Where indicated, 0.05% Tyloxapol was included to prevent bacterial clumping. Assays were conducted following the Microdilution Alamar Blue Assay (MABA) protocol as previously described (**PMID 25779323**). Briefly, mid-log phase *M. tuberculosis* cultures were diluted 1:1,000 and added to 384-well plates containing serially diluted compounds. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 7 days. Alamar Blue and 20% Tween 80 were then added to each well to assess cell viability. Plates were read 24 h later at 570 nm with a 600 nm reference wavelength. MBC values were determined by plating aliquots from wells at or above the MIC onto solid

medium. The MBC was defined as the lowest concentration at which no colony formation was observed. A compound was considered bactericidal if the MBC/MIC ratio was ≤ 4 (PMID **14999632**).

Cytotoxicity Assay. HEK293T and HepG2 cells (ATCC) were cultured in DMEM (Gibco, Cat# 31053-028) supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1 \times penicillin-streptomycin (Gibco). For HepG2 cells, the medium was additionally supplemented with 1 \times GlutaMAX (Gibco) and 1 mM sodium pyruvate (Gibco). Cells were maintained at 37 °C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂. Prior to seeding, cells were washed twice with 1 \times DPBS (Gibco), incubated with TrypLE (Gibco) at 37 °C for 10 minutes, and washed once in propagation medium. Cell viability was assessed by seeding 5 μ L of a suspension containing 5 \times 10⁴ cells/well into 1,536-well plates containing a 3-fold serial dilution of compounds (ranging from 40 μ M to 2 nM). Plates were incubated for 72 hours under standard culture conditions. After incubation, 2 μ L of CellTiter-Glo[®] Luminescent Cell Viability Reagent (Promega), diluted 1:1 in water, was added to each well. Luminescence was measured using a PHERAStar plate reader (BMG Labtech). Data were normalized to DMSO-treated wells (negative control) and puromycin-treated wells (10 μ M, positive control). Dose-response curves were fitted using the Smart Fit function in Genedata Screener Analyzer (v16.0.8).

Intramacrophage activity of compounds in THP-1 cells. THP-1 monocytes (ATCC TIB-202) were cultured and passaged in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 50 μ M 2-mercaptoethanol (Gibco) at 37 °C with 5% CO₂. For differentiation, cells were seeded at 1 \times 10⁵ cells/mL in medium containing 50 nM phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) and incubated overnight under the same conditions. *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv expressing the *luxCDABE* operon (*Mtb-lux*) was grown to mid-log phase, diluted in propagation medium, and used to infect the differentiated THP-1 macrophages at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 1:1. After 24 hours, infected cells were washed twice with PBS, resuspended in fresh medium, detached by scraping, and counted. Cells were then seeded into compound-containing 96-well plates at a final density of 1 \times 10⁵ cells/well. Intracellular luminescence was measured on day 3 post-infection using a Clariostar Plus plate reader (BMG Labtech). Data were normalized to negative control (DMSO) and positive control (rifampicin, 10 μ M) using Genedata Screener Analyzer (v16.0.8). All compound concentrations were tested in technical triplicate.

Kill Kinetics Assay. *M. tuberculosis* cultures were grown to an optical density of 0.2 at 595 nm, then diluted 1:10 in fresh medium. Test compounds were added at concentrations corresponding to 10 \times their respective MICs. At defined time points (days 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, and 24), 200 μ L aliquots were collected. From each sample, 100 μ L was serially diluted in triplicate, plated on solid medium, and incubated for 4 to 6 weeks at 37 °C. Bacterial viability was quantified by enumerating colony-forming units (CFU).

Isolation of Resistant Mutants and Their Genetic Characterization. *M. tuberculosis* cultures in mid-log phase ($\sim 1 \times 10^8$ CFU/mL) were plated onto Middlebrook 7H10 agar supplemented with either glycerol or cholesterol along with test compounds at 4 \times and 10 \times their MIC values. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for six weeks to allow the emergence of resistant colonies. Individual colonies were isolated, expanded in liquid culture, and subjected to MIC determination to confirm resistance. Genomic DNA from resistant mutants was extracted using the cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB)–lysozyme method. DNA

libraries were prepared using the TruSeq DNA Whole Genome Sequencing kit (Illumina) and sequenced on either a NovaSeq or NextSeq platform (TxGen, Texas A&M University) using 150 bp paired-end reads. Sequencing reads were aligned to a resequenced reference genome of the parental *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv strain using BWA software. Variants were identified using in-house analysis pipelines, including single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and insertions/deletions (indels). Variant calls were filtered to include only those at genomic positions with read depth >20× and allele purity >70%. To estimate resistance frequency, the total viable bacterial count was determined by serial dilution plating on drug-free medium. Resistance frequency was calculated as the number of resistant colonies divided by the total CFU plated. All experiments were performed in at least three independent biological replicates to ensure reproducibility and statistical confidence.

Hu-Coates 100-day-old culture model. *M. tuberculosis* was cultured in 10 mL of Middlebrook 7H9 broth supplemented with 10% OADC and 0.025% Tween 80 in 25-mL screw-cap Nunc tubes. Cultures were incubated statically at 37 °C for 100 days to allow the development of a non-replicating, persistent population. To disrupt bacterial clumps prior to treatment, cultures were subjected to low-intensity sonication using a Branson 1800 water bath sonicator. The sonication procedure consisted of three 2-minute pulses separated by 1-minute rest intervals, with vortexing between pulses. To assess bactericidal activity, 100-day-old cultures were treated with individual compounds or compound combinations and incubated for 5 days at 37 °C. Following treatment, cultures were washed three times with PBS to remove residual drug. Bacterial viability was quantified by serial dilution and plating on Middlebrook 7H11 agar supplemented with 10% OADC. Colony-forming units (CFUs) were enumerated after appropriate incubation (PMID **18173880**).

Lobel's Nutrient deprivation model Exponential-phase *M. tuberculosis* cultures (OD₆₀₀ 0.4–0.6) were pelleted, washed with PBS containing 0.025% Tween 80, and incubated in the same medium at 37 °C for 6 weeks to induce nutrient starvation. Cultures were then exposed to compounds for 7 days, and bacterial viability was assessed by CFU enumeration on 7H11-OADC agar plates (PMID **28196957**).

¹H NMR of P1

¹H NMR of P1B

¹H NMR of P2

Current Data Parameters
 NAME 450233-CAVENDISH
 EXPNO 1
 PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
 Date 20230515
 Time 15.19 h
 INSTRUM Avance
 PROBHD z163739 0756 ()
 PULPROG zg30
 TD 40000
 SOLVENT DMSO
 NS 64
 DS 0
 SWH 10000.000 Hz
 FIDRES 0.500000 Hz
 AQ 2.0000000 sec
 RG 101
 DW 50.000 usec
 DE 11.14 usec
 TE 294.3 K
 D1 1.0000000 sec
 TD0 1
 SF01 400.6024737 MHz
 NUC1 1H
 P0 2.67 usec
 P1 8.00 usec
 PLW1 21.40600014 W

F2 - Processing parameters
 SI 65536
 SF 400.6000000 MHz
 WDW EM
 SSB 0
 LB 0.10 Hz
 GB 0
 PC 1.00

¹H NMR of P3

Current Data Parameters
 NAME 473141-Cavendish
 EXPNO 1
 PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
 Date 20230602
 Time 22.30
 INSTRUM spect
 PROBHD 5 mm PABBO BB/
 PULPROG zg30
 TD 19998
 SOLVENT DMSO
 NS 6
 DS 0
 SWH 10000.000 Hz
 FIDRES 0.500050 Hz
 AQ 0.9999000 sec
 RG 203
 DW 50.000 usec
 DE 6.50 usec
 TE 294.2 K
 D1 1.0000000 sec
 TD0 1

===== CHANNEL f1 =====
 SF01 400.1324710 MHz
 NUC1 1H
 P1 14.00 usec
 PLW1 16.00000000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
 SI 65536
 SF 400.1300030 MHz
 WDW EM
 SSB 0
 LB 0.30 Hz
 GB 0
 PC 1.00

¹H NMR of P4

¹H NMR of P5

¹H NMR of P6

¹H NMR of P7

¹H NMR of P8

¹H NMR of P9

¹H NMR of P10

¹H NMR of P11

¹H NMR of P14

¹H NMR of P15

¹H NMR of P16

¹H NMR of P17

¹H NMR of P18

¹H NMR of P19

¹H NMR of P20

Confidential

¹H NMR of P21

¹H NMR of P22


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Current Data Parameters
NAME      469064-CAVENDISH
EXPNO     1
PROCNO    1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_     20230531
Time      10.12
INSTRUM   spect
PROBHD    5 mm PABBO BB/
PULPROG   zg30
TD         19998
SOLVENT   DMSO
NS         96
DS         0
SWH        10000.000 Hz
FIDRES     0.500050 Hz
AQ         0.9999000 sec
RG         203
DW         50.000 usec
DE         6.50 usec
TE         294.1 K
D1         1.00000000 sec
TD0        1

===== CHANNEL f1 =====
SFO1      400.1324710 MHz
NUC1      1H
P1        14.00 usec
PLW1      16.00000000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI         65536
SF         400.1300032 MHz
WDW        EM
SSB        0
LB         0.10 Hz
GB         0
PC         1.00
    
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¹H NMR of P23


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Current Data Parameters
NAME      461664-Cavendish
EXPNO     1
PROCNO    1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_     20230524
Time      20.25 h
INSTRUM   Avance
PROBHD    Z163739_0756 (
PULPROG   zg30
TD         40000
SOLVENT   DMSO
NS         16
DS         0
SWH        10000.000 Hz
FIDRES     0.500000 Hz
AQ         2.0000000 sec
RG         101
DW         50.000 usec
DE         11.14 usec
TE         293.5 K
D1         1.00000000 sec
TD0        1
SFO1      400.6024737 MHz
NUC1      1H
P0         2.67 usec
P1         8.00 usec
PLW1      21.40600014 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI         65536
SF         400.6000000 MHz
WDW        EM
SSB        0
LB         0.10 Hz
GB         0
PC         1.00
    
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¹H NMR of P24

¹H NMR of P25

¹H NMR of P26

Current Data Parameters
 NAME 481940-Cavendish
 EXPNO 1
 PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
 Date_ 20230610
 Time 8.33 h
 INSTRUM Avance
 PROBHD Z163739_0756 (
 PULPROG zg30
 TD 40000
 SOLVENT DMSO
 NS 16
 DS 0
 SWH 10000.000 Hz
 FIDRES 0.500000 Hz
 AQ 2.0000000 sec
 RG 101
 DW 50.000 usec
 DE 11.14 usec
 TE 295.0 K
 D1 1.00000000 sec
 TD0 1
 SFO1 400.6024737 MHz
 NUC1 1H
 P0 2.67 usec
 P1 8.00 usec
 PLW1 21.40600014 W

F2 - Processing parameters
 SI 65536
 SF 400.6000000 MHz
 WDW EM
 SSB 0
 LB 0.10 Hz
 GB 0
 PC 1.00

¹H NMR of P27

Current Data Parameters
 NAME 475864-Cavendish
 EXPNO 1
 PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
 Date_ 20230606
 Time 20.12 h
 INSTRUM Avance
 PROBHD Z163739_0756 (
 PULPROG zg30
 TD 40000
 SOLVENT DMSO
 NS 16
 DS 0
 SWH 10000.000 Hz
 FIDRES 0.500000 Hz
 AQ 2.0000000 sec
 RG 101
 DW 50.000 usec
 DE 11.14 usec
 TE 296.0 K
 D1 1.00000000 sec
 TD0 1
 SFO1 400.6024737 MHz
 NUC1 1H
 P0 2.67 usec
 P1 8.00 usec
 PLW1 21.40600014 W

F2 - Processing parameters
 SI 65536
 SF 400.6000000 MHz
 WDW EM
 SSB 0
 LB 0.10 Hz
 GB 0
 PC 1.00

¹H NMR of P28

¹H NMR of P29

¹H NMR of P30

¹H NMR of P31

¹H NMR of P32

¹H NMR of P33

¹H NMR of P34

¹H NMR of P35

¹H NMR of P36

¹H NMR of P37

¹H NMR of P38

¹H NMR of P39

¹H NMR of P40

Current Data Parameters
NAME 640041-Cavendish
EXPNO 1
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20231101
Time 8.40 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD Z108618_0769 (
PULPROG zg30
TD 16384
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 16
DS 0
SHE 8012.820 Hz
FIDRES 0.978127 Hz
AQ 1.0223616 sec
RG 201.52
DW 62.400 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 334.5 K
D1 1.00000000 sec
TDO 1
SFO1 400.3024720 MHz
NUC1 1H
P0 5.00 usec
P1 15.00 usec
PLW1 14.00000000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 6536
SF 400.2999993 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 0.30 Hz
GB 0
PC 1.00